

ANATOMICAL AND PHYSIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE STRUCTURE OF SOFT TISSUES AROUND THE IMPLANT, AFFECTING THE LONG-TERM RESULT OF IMPLANTOLOGICAL TREATMENT (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract. *The quantity and quality of bone tissue, as well as the condition of soft tissues around dental implants, are among the most important factors determining the long-term clinical outcome of implantation. There are many reasons why it is important to pay attention to the condition of soft tissues around implants. Factors such as a shallow vestibule, the level of attachment of the frenulum of the lips can affect the development of periodontal pathology in 1.4-2.5% of cases. Many people believe that the structural features of the tissues and organs of the oral cavity, or the biotype (phenotype) of the periodontal tissues, are of great importance for the stability of periodontal tissues. It has now been established that the surface topography of the implant plays an important role in the processes of osseointegration, causing, in particular, the risk of periimplantitis [70, 137, 73]. The article presents literature data describing the most common causes of soft tissue recession in the area of dental implants and the criteria for a successful outcome of implant treatment. Purpose of the research is to study the literature data on the most common causes of soft tissue recession in the area of dental implants. The review and analysis of literary sources was carried out using keywords on the electronic resources of the Scopus, Web of Science, Med Line, The Cochrane Library, and Russian Science Citation Index databases. Foreign and domestic sources were used to write the review article. Insufficient width of the attached keratinized gingiva zone and high mobility of soft tissues lead to unsatisfactory aesthetic and functional results. The aesthetic result of implant treatment will not be perfect in the absence of gingival papillae, non-physiological gingival contour and soft tissue recession. One of the important biological parameters, such as biological width, gingival complex, position of the bone margin, width, etc., is the concept of gingival biotype. While planning dental implantation, it is necessary to take into account the gingival biotype to predict the results of the operation in order to maximally preserve the volume and width of the attached mucosa.*

Keywords: *dental implantation, gingival recession, osseointegration, keratinized gingiva.*

It is important to suggest that as a result of the tissue regeneration process around the neck of dental implants, the so-called soft tissue attachment is created, the main function of which is to prevent infection of bone tissue from the oral cavity. Despite the similarity of the histological structure of the gum around the teeth and the mucous membrane in contact with the cervical part of dental implants, there are some differences in their structure.

Definitely, the outer surface of the free gum is covered with a multilayered squamous keratinized epithelium, which passes into the barrier epithelium facing the surface of the abutment. The barrier epithelium is represented by several rows of cells. Epithelial structures are replaced by connective tissue approximately 2 mm apical to the border of soft tissues at a distance of 1-1.5 mm

from the alveolar ridge. The connective tissue around the tooth differs from that surrounding the implant by the presence of cement, from which the dent gingival and dent gingival collagen fibers extend [1]. Around the implant, the collagen fibers are oriented differently: starting in the periosteum of the alveolar ridge, they are located parallel to the implant surface, without attaching to it [5].

Besides that, the connective tissue of the supra-alveolar layer near the implants contains more collagen fibers, but fewer fibroblasts and blood vessels than around the teeth [1].

Along the perimeter, there is mobile connective tissue, well supplied with vessels. At the same time, directly at the surface of the implant, there is a wide layer of dense fibers 50-100 μm thick, poor in blood vessels. Thus, collagen fibers form a dense ligament around the dental implant, the stability of which largely depends on their attachment to the periosteum of the alveolar bone. The blood supply to the soft tissues in the peri-implant area occurs through the terminal branches of the large vessels of the periosteum, and not from the periodontal gap, as in a natural tooth. For this reason, the nutrition of the soft tissues around the implant is less abundant than around the tooth. [2]

Different parameters are used to quantitatively characterize the gingival tissues, in particular, biological width, gingival thickness, height and width of the alveoli [12].

A frequently used parameter is biological width - the length of the tissue complex (connective tissue and attached epithelium) above the peri-implant bone tissue, similar to the natural periodontium. [14].

Along with these data, the researchers found that there is a certain proportional relationship between the width of the gingival groove, the thickness of the marginal epithelium and connective tissue attachment, which are on average 0.69 mm, 0.97 mm and 1.07 mm, respectively. Biological width is the sum of the sizes of the marginal epithelium and connective tissue attachment, on average equal to 2.04 mm. [18] This physiologically formed value is also determined by the contours of the alveolar bone and is assessed individually: under anesthesia, a flat periodontal probe is used to measure the distance to the alveolar bone, and the depth of the gingival groove is subtracted from the result. Around the implant, the biological width increases and is 3.0 ± 0.5 mm. For sub gingivally healing implants, this value is somewhat larger (about 3.8 mm) than for implants that heal trans gingivally (about 2.73 mm) [17].

Additionally, it can be explained by the presence of a micro gap that is formed after the implant is opened and the abutment is fixed at the junction of the intraosseous part of the implant with the supporting element. [16].

The junctional epithelium plays a key role in maintaining a healthy periodontium: it creates an epithelial attachment, ensuring a tight connection of soft tissues with the tooth surface; it is permeable and ensures the removal of metabolic products of plaque bacteria (toxins, chemotaxins, antigens, etc.). In the opposite direction, the body's protective elements (serum exudate, antibodies, etc.) diffuse. Even in the absence of clinical signs of inflammation, polymorphonuclear leukocytes constantly migrate through the junctional epithelium into the gingival sulcus. Connective tissue attachment is formed around titanium and aluminum-based ceramic abutments. When using gold alloys and dental ceramics, the connective tissue zone is displaced in the apical direction, and the biological width increases [15].

In both periodontology and implantology, there is a concept of "tissue biotype", which includes the following parameters:

- the presence or absence of keratinized gingiva
 - the thickness and width of keratinized gingiva;
 - the height and width of the gingival papillae;
 - the height and width of the alveolar process of the maxilla and the alveolar margin of the mandible;
- the level of attachment of the facial and masticatory muscles; the shape of the crown of the teeth. [13].

There are many reasons why it is important to pay attention to the condition of the soft tissues around the implants. Factors such as a shallow vestibule and the level of attachment of the frenulum of the lips can affect the development of periodontal pathology in 1.4-2.5% of cases [11].

According to many, the structural features of the tissues and organs of the oral cavity, or the biotype (phenotype) of the periodontal tissues, are of great importance for the stability of periodontal tissues [10].

Additionally, there are thick and thin biotypes of the gum. It is also advisable to take into account the so-called average biotype. With a thick biotype of the gum, the shrinkage of the soft tissues after tooth extraction occurs in a minimal amount. With a thin biotype of the gum and atrophy of the alveolar ridge, the decrease in the width of the zone of attached keratinized gum is very significant. With a minimal amount of keratinized gum in the adentia zone, the installation of a dental implant can lead to its reduction or its complete absence. Insufficient width of the attached keratinized gingiva zone and high mobility of soft tissues lead to unsatisfactory aesthetic and functional results.

Besides that, the mobile mucous membrane surrounding a natural tooth or dental implant is constantly shifting when opening the mouth, eating, and performing hygiene procedures. Due to insufficient hygiene with mobile soft tissues, inflammation develops with subsequent gum recession. [9]

Non-keratinized tissue is more easily injured. As a result, when food debris accumulates in the area of the papillary and marginal gingiva, an inflammatory process occurs. The involvement of inflammatory cells leads to increased osteoclast activity and disruption of the osseointegration process around the implant. Another cause of bone resorption is impaired blood supply due to a deficiency of attached gingiva. [8]

In addition, a number of authors indicate that any orthopedic structure made of both medical titanium alloy and zirconium oxide is visible through a gum less than 1.5-2.0 mm thick. Thus, it is generally accepted that for dental implantation to be successful, the thickness of the keratinized gum should be at least 2 mm.

Definitely, the aesthetic result of implant treatment will not be perfect in the absence of gingival papillae, non-physiological gum contour and soft tissue recession. The zone of attached keratinized gum around the implant affects both the clinical and immunological parameters of these areas. Its sufficient width is protection against mechanical injuries of any kind, makes it possible to carry out easy and effective control over the formation of microbial plaque and soft dental plaque, and in the aesthetically significant area of the oral cavity contributes to a longer stable result. A differentiated approach to the choice of the method of correction of the vestibule of the oral cavity in various clinical situations allows achieving the best treatment results. The success of implantological treatment, namely ensuring long-term aesthetic and functional stability, also depends on the correct 3D positioning of the implant relative to the future orthopedic structure.

This is especially important when planning implantation in an aesthetically significant zone [7]. Primary stabilization is defined as biomechanical stability immediately upon implant placement and in the postoperative period will be extremely dependent on the formation of young bone tissue at the border with the implant during the healing process [6]. Also, in addition to the quality and quantity of bone tissue, the achievement of adequate primary stability is influenced by the macrodesign of the implant, the characteristics of its surface and the protocol for preparing the bed for the implant [4].

Conclusion. By summarizing it can be suggested that the presence of the required volume of keratinized gingiva is of great importance around the superstructures of the dental implant, as a dense attached cuff is formed and thus protection against the penetration of bacteria to the implant is provided. Attached keratinized gingiva and bone crest are the main functional barrier between the dental implant and the oral cavity.

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